

Response to “Mismatch Between Million Veteran Program Genome-Wide Association Study Summary Statistics and dbSNP Reveals Reference/Alternate Assignment Error”

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In July 2024, the VA Million Veteran Program (MVP) (1) published a multi-population genome-wide association study of 2,068 traits from 635,969 United States Veteran participants (2). This publication was accompanied by deposition of summary statistics into dbGaP (accession number phs002453) for public download, as well as an MVP-specific PheWeb (3) browser (<https://phenomics.va.ornl.gov/>) for data visualization. In their letter, Liu, Chen, Liao, and Tsai have raised concerns about discrepancies between the data in dbGaP and reference information in dbSNP, as well as in data presentation between dbGaP and PheWeb (4). We appreciate their documentation of these differences. The differences they report, however, are due to differences in notation and do not affect the scientific integrity of the results.

Firstly, we wish to define some terms to provide clarity in further discussions. dbSNP uses “reference” (REF_{dbSNP}) to refer to the reference allele from the genome reference build and “alternate” (ALT_{dbSNP}) to define any deviations from this. All information for a particular

variant is housed within the same RefSNP identifier (rsid), regardless of the number of alternative allele possibilities. Thus, a single ID in dbGaP may comprise multiple alternative alleles. The “reference” (REF_{MVP}) and “alternate” (ALT_{MVP}) alleles in the MVP dbGaP files refer to the alleles tested in the analysis and are not necessarily aligned to REF_{dbSNP} & ALT_{dbSNP} . We therefore included the “effect” allele (EA) for which the odds ratios or effect sizes were reported, along with the effect allele frequency (EAF). This information allows the user to easily align the reported results to either of the alleles they wish. Although the results are unambiguously presented, we acknowledge and regret that our use of the terms “reference” and “alternate” in labelling the alleles has led to confusion and appreciate this opportunity to clarify our presentation of the summary statistics.

We believe the discrepancies reported by Liu and colleagues between the MVP data deposited in dbGaP and dbSNP version 153 are explained by the lack of harmonization of REF_{MVP}/ALT_{MVP} and REF_{dbSNP}/ALT_{dbSNP} and the presence of SNPs with multiple alternate alleles. To test this, we used the same MVP results (Phe_571 (EUR)) and dbSNP version as the authors and compared allele frequencies. When we performed the analysis assuming equivalence REF_{MVP}/ALT_{MVP} and REF_{dbSNP}/ALT_{dbSNP} , we achieved similar results. Matching on the alleles themselves, rather than the REF/ALT designation, resolved all discrepancies (**Figure 1**). This is also demonstrated by comparing the MVP “ea” and “af” columns with the dbSNP_153 “Ref”, “Alt”, and “Freq” in their Table as presented in **Table 1**.

We also note there are differences between the way the data is presented on PheWeb and in dbGaP due to post-processing of data for display in PheWeb. There are some views in PheWeb where the effect allele was not explicitly stated therefore it was decided to align the effect to the minor allele, which is most cases is ALT_{dbSNP} . As a result, EA might be flipped relative to dbGAP files. While this can create apparent differences, all transformations preserve the biological meaning of the results.

In summary, we agree that allele representation differs across dbGaP and PheWeb, and in relation to the dbSNP reference. However, all underlying summary statistics are consistent, identical, and valid, simply presented using different conventions. By interpreting odds ratios and effect sizes with respect to the clearly labeled effect allele, as well as matching data by the pair of tested alleles, researchers can confidently use this resource.

References

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Figure 1: Comparison of Merging Results between Million Veteran Program Summary Statistics and dbSNP Using Different Methods.

	Distribution of Ref/Alt Comparison Outcomes Between Summary Statistics and dbSNP.	Differences in Allele Frequencies Between dbSNP and Million Veteran Program Summary Statistics
Liu et al (2025)	<p>MVP EA Frequency</p> <p>dbSNP REF Frequency</p>	
Assuming REF_{MVP}/ALT_{MVP} equals REF_{dbSNP}/ALT_{dbSNP}	<p>MVP EA Frequency</p> <p>dbSNP REF Frequency</p>	
Matching allele pairs regardless of REF/ALT designation	<p>dbSNP REF Frequency (MVP)</p> <p>dbSNP REF Frequency (dbSNP)</p>	

*At least one allele matched between MVP and dbSNP for 0.46%. The remaining 0.14% were all insertions/deletions which are known to be difficult to match due to varying naming conventions for alleles.

Table 1 – Comparison of Allele Frequencies between Million Veteran Program Summary Statistics and dbSNP Using Different Merging Methods. Table presents selected columns from Table 1 of Lui et al. (4), which were then annotated with the alleles matched based on allele pairs regardless of REF/ALT designation.

SNP_ID	CHROM	POS	MVP				dbSNP_153			RefAlt_Stat	Matched Allele	Frequency	
			REF	ALT	EA	AF	REF	ALT	Freq			MVP	dbSNP
rs738408	22	43928850	T	C	C	0.7783	C	T	0.7378	Flipped	C	0.7783	0.7378
rs9506776	13	22046711	C	T	T	0.3367	T	C	0.4643	Flipped	T	0.3367	0.4643
rs139012393	8	106870174	C	G	G	0.9968	G	C	0.9934	Flipped	G	0.9968	0.9934
rs12157831	22	34172234	T	C	C	0.9983	C	T	0.9661	Flipped	C	0.9983	0.9661
rs60955927	6	159747863	A	G	G	0.9995	G	A	0.9778	Flipped	G	0.9995	0.9778
rs4661178	1	156551492	G	T	T	0.9441	T	G	N.A.	Flipped	T	0.9441	NA
rs34316680	10	66734229	A	T	T	0.9885	T	A	0.9415	Flipped	T	0.9885	0.9415
rs556253434	11	46212152	C	T	T	0.9996	T	C	0.9996	Flipped	T	0.9996	0.9996
rs75888017	11	2170603	A	G	G	0.9998	G	A	0.9982	Flipped	G	0.9998	0.9982
rs186521773	1	118362739	A	G	G	0.9996	G	A	0.9992	Flipped	G	0.9996	0.9992
rs61813631	1	155895251	C	T	T	0.9851	T	C	0.9966	Flipped	T	0.9851	0.9966
rs535602139	5	132184240	A	G	G	0.9943	G	T	0.001597	Mismatch	G	0.9943	0.9984*
rs62069787	17	70506202	A	G	G	0.9775	G	A	0.9946	Flipped	G	0.9775	0.9946
rs4272700	10	27592379	A	T	T	0.7119	T	A	0.8375	Flipped	T	0.7119	0.8375
rs565984041	3	147500150	A	G	G	0.9997	G	A	0.9996	Flipped	G	0.9997	0.9996

*Lui et al reported the incorrect frequency from dbSNP for the REF allele for this SNP